

YOGA POSTURE ESTIMATION & CORRECTION

Mr. Roopesh Kumar B N¹, Pavan M², Pavan P³, Shravya M R⁴, Vikas Kashyap R⁵

¹Associate Professor, ^{2,3,4,5}Under Graduate Student

Dept of Computer Science and Engineering, K S Institute of Technology, Bengaluru, Karnataka.

Abstract: In this research, a novel method for image processing and MediaPipe-based real-time yoga stance recognition and correction is presented. The technology recognises important body markers on the practitioner by utilising MediaPipe's posture estimate capabilities, which allows for accurate analysis of yoga poses. Pose mistakes and common misalignments are found using unique methods. Users receive immediate visual or audio feedback from the device that directs them towards proper alignment. By providing feedback, this system seeks to raise practitioners' awareness of appropriate alignment of their as well as the efficiency and security yoga practice.

Keywords: MediaPipe, Image processing, Flask, Html, JavaScript, Pre-processing, Feature Extraction, Segmentation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Owing to its many health advantages, yoga, a comprehensive discipline that includes physical postures, breathing exercises, and meditation, has become more popular. However, it can be difficult for practitioners, especially new ones, to learn yoga positions because they call for precise alignment and skill. Advances in image processing and computer vision technology have created new opportunities for automated pose recognition and correction systems in recent years, giving practitioners instantaneous feedback. This study presents a novel method for yoga stance recognition and correction based on image processing techniques and MediaPipe, a flexible framework for building perception pipelines.

This system uses Body Mass Index (BMI) analytics in addition to pose identification and correction to give yoga practitioners individualised insights into their practices. A popular statistic for evaluating body composition is BMI, which provides useful information about a person's weight status in relation to their height. Practitioners can learn more about how their body composition affects their yoga practice by including BMI analytics into the yoga pose detection and correction system. This all-encompassing strategy attempts to maximise the effectiveness and security of yoga exercises by customising critiques and suggestions according to personal traits.

A number of significant issues with traditional yoga practice are intended to be addressed by the proposed approach, such as the difficulty of self-evaluation, the possibility of damage from improper posture, and the absence of individualised instruction. Through the utilisation of MediaPipe for precise pose identification and correction in conjunction with image processing techniques, the system offers practitioners instantaneous feedback, assisting them in attaining appropriate alignment and technique. Moreover, the incorporation of BMI analytics provides practitioners with understanding of their body composition, enabling well-informed choices and customised modifications to their yoga routine. All things considered, this work offers a thorough framework for yoga pose identification and correction that is enhanced by BMI analytics to improve the efficiency and security of yoga exercises. It is possible to validate the system's effectiveness and usability through experimental assessment and user research, Paving the way for its integration into mainstream yoga practices and wellness applications.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

No.	Title	Journal	Methodology	Outcome	Limitations/Future Scope
1.	"Infinity yoga Tutor"	International Journal of Computer Applications	Utilized OpenPose, a real-time pose estimation model based on deep learning	Real-time yoga pose detection with low computational requirements; suitable for real-world applications	May struggle with complex poses or variations
2.	"Yoga Pose detection and classification using deep learning"	International Journal of Computer applications	Transfer learning from a pre-trained deep learning model on a large dataset	Improved performance on a small annotated yoga pose dataset; reduced need for a large labeled dataset	Relying on technology may discourage practitioners from developing their own body awareness and mindfulness

3. PROPOSED ALGORITHM

1. Data Acquisition: Obtain a dataset comprising pictures of different yoga poses along with the corresponding ground truth annotations, such as angle values or keypoint locations. Convert these annotations to a CSV file format so that access and comparison can be made easier while the algorithm runs.
2. Image Processing with MediaPipe: To conduct keypoint detection on video input recorded by a camera, use the MediaPipe library. MediaPipe's posture estimate model can be used to extract keypoint coordinates or calculate angle values for important body joints.
3. Angle Calculation: For every yoga pose, identify a particular set of important bodily joints and the angles that correspond to them. Determine these angles using the MediaPipe model's keypoint coordinates.
4. CSV File Comparison: Open the CSV file containing each yoga pose's ground truth angle data. Compare the ground truth angles contained in the CSV file with the computed angles that were produced in step 3.
5. Posture Classification: Establish a tolerance level or threshold for angle variation in order to assess how accurately a posture is executed. Sort each position by determining how close the computed angles are to the ground truth angles.

6. Integration and Deployment: Incorporate the refined algorithm into an intuitive application or platform intended for the real-time estimate of yoga posture. Provide feedback systems so that users can examine and modify posture estimations as needed.

4. METHODOLOGY

The fitness application's methodology is made to offer a customised, interactive workout, guaranteeing that users can successfully meet their fitness objectives. Here's a more thorough explanation:

1. Landing Page Engagement: The visitor is welcomed by an eye-catching landing page that gives a synopsis of the application's capabilities as soon as they arrive at the application. This page is purposefully created to pique the user's curiosity and direct them to the login page.
2. Secure Login Procedure: After entering their credentials, the user is taken to the login screen. The privacy of the user's workout history and preferences, as well as the protection of their personal data, depend on this secure procedure.
3. Personal Data Retrieval: The programme retrieves the user's personal information, including height, weight, age, and fitness goals, when they log in. This information is necessary to customise the exercise programme to the individual demands and objectives of the user.
4. BMI Calculation and Analysis: The application determines the user's Body Mass Index (BMI) based on their personal data, giving them a better understanding of their overall fitness and health. Setting sensible and achievable weight goals requires taking this crucial step.
5. Goal Weight Determination: To establish an ideal goal weight, the application considers the user's own fitness objectives together with an analysis of their BMI. The user's lifestyle and degree of exercise are just two of the many variables that must be carefully taken into account during this procedure.
6. Customised Workout Creation: After the target weight is determined, the application creates a personalised training schedule. The activities in this plan are tailored to the user's fitness level and focus on areas that will most effectively help them attain their goal weight.

7. **Interactive Workout Initiation:** The application offers interactive instructions for every activity as soon as the user begins. To make sure the user is executing each movement correctly, this also contains real-time feedback, good form examples, and comprehensive instructions.
8. **Real-Time Posture Monitoring:** Using cutting-edge technology, the application actively tracks the user's posture during the exercise. The application instantly steps in with remedial feedback if it detects any deviations from the proper form, assisting the user in promptly correcting their posture.
9. **Workout Duration Tracking:** By recording the entire amount of time spent working out, the application enables users to track their endurance and stamina over time. Those who want to progressively raise the intensity of their workouts may find this feature quite helpful.
10. **Comprehensive Analytics Compilation:** The programme gathers a vast array of analytics after an exercise. This contains information about the user's overall performance, workout time, and posture accuracy, all of which are useful for planning future workouts.
11. **Data and Progress Presentation:** Lastly, the user is shown the workout analytics data. With the help of this comprehensive report, which identifies areas of success and areas for development, the user will be better equipped to make decisions on their fitness path.

With the help of this meticulous process, customers can be sure that they are tracking their fitness goals, getting customised training programmes, and getting useful information that will help them keep getting healthier and more fit. For anyone trying to improve their workout experience, the application's interactive features and real-time feedback mechanisms make it a useful resource.

5. IMPLEMENTATION DIAGRAM

6. RESULTS

YOGA POSTURE Analytics

suryanamaskara1

Left_elbow	24
Left_shoulder	14
Right_shoulder	15
Right_elbow	21
Left_hip	173
Left_knee	178
Right_hip	175
Right_knee	177

Surya Namaskar

Youtube Link:
[Suryanamaskara](#)

localhost:5000/analytic.html

Analytics

Username is:pavan

Time Spent in Seconds:54

Calories Burnt:6.75

SHOW

Go Back

7. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The fitness application may see a number of user-centric upgrades in the future. By enabling users to share their accomplishments and take part in challenges, improving the app's social connectivity may promote community involvement. By adding more diverse routines to the exercise library, a greater range of fitness levels and tastes may be accommodated. A more comprehensive approach to health would be provided by including a nutrition tracking tool that would assist users in matching their food to their exercise objectives. To make working out more enjoyable and rewarding, gamification components might also be added. This could increase user motivation and retention. By making these improvements, the fitness platform should become more comprehensive and interesting, motivating users to keep up a healthy lifestyle.

8. REFERENCES

- [1] "Yoga tutor visualisation and analysis using SURF algorithm," S. Patil, A. Pawar, A. Peshave, A. N. Ansari, and A. Navada, Proceedings of the 2011 IEEE Control and System Graduate Research Colloquium, pp. 43–46, IEEE, Shah Alam, Malaysia, June 2011.
- [2] The work "Learning and self-instruction expert system for Yoga" was presented by Wu, Yin, and Guo in the Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop on Intelligent Systems and Applications, held in May 2010 in Mumbai, India. The paper was published on pages 1-4.
- [3] "Computer-assisted self-training system for sports exercise using kinects," H. T. Chen, Y. Z. He, C. L. Chou, S. Y. Lee, B. S. P. Lin, and J. Y. Yu, Proceedings of the 2013 IEEE International Conference on Multimedia and Expo Workshops (ICMEW), pp. 1-4, IEEE, London, UK, July 2013.
- [4] In the Proceedings of the 2018 2nd International Conference on Robotics and Automation Sciences (ICRAS), pp. 1–5, IEEE, Wuhan, China, June 2018, E. W. Trejo and P. Yuan, "Recognition of Yoga poses through an interactive system with Kinect device."
- [5] Robust pose recognition using deep learning, A. Mohanty, A. Ahmed, T. Goswami, A. Das, P. Vaishnavi, and R. R. Sahay, Proceedings of the International Conference on Computer Vision and Image Processing, pp. 93–105, Springer, Singapore, December 2017.